

ESTIMATION OF STRENGTH AND FRACTURE TOUGHNESS FOR NANOMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

A molecular-continuum model proposed in our previous study for the estimation of elastic stiffness of nanomaterials is modified in this paper for the estimation of strength and fracture toughness. To predict yield strength and ultimate strength, a uniformly tensile strain state is assumed. As to the prediction of fracture toughness, the crack near tip deformation obtained from the linear elastic fracture mechanics is assumed. After setting the proper deformation field, the changes of bond distance and bond angle between atoms can be obtained. With this information and the proper potential energy function of molecular mechanics, the potential energy which is treated as strain energy in the deformed solids can be calculated. Similar process can be done when a small advance is added on the crack, and then the strain energy release rate can be obtained. With the above calculation procedure and the known relation between strain energy release rate and stress intensity factor, the estimation of strength and fracture toughness becomes possible for the nanomaterials. To illustrate the proposed method, the strength and fracture toughness of a graphene sheet is estimated. The numerical results fall in the reasonable range obtained by the other methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past two decades, graphene sheets and carbon nanotubes have drawn many researchers' attention because of their special and useful properties like mechanical, electrical and thermal properties [1-3]. Although there are some experimental works measuring the stiffness, strength and toughness of nanomaterials such as [4-7], due to the difficulties to get stable and trustable experimental results, recently a lot of efforts have been put on the estimation of their mechanical properties through theoretical and numerical simulation. In general, the simulation methods employed in the literature can be categorized into: atomic model, continuum model, and molecular-continuum model. Li and Chou proposed continuum model such as structural mechanics finite element method [8]. This model is widely used to estimate the elastic properties by other researchers. The ideas of using analytical molecular mechanics model to find the elastic properties of graphene sheets and carbon nanotubes are proposed thereafter [9-18]. Owing to the difficulties of setting fracture criterion, most of the simulation methods focus on stiffness instead of strength and toughness.

Molecular dynamics was used to obtain the stress-strain response to describe the elastic, plastic and fracture behavior [19-22], and find the abrupt deviation of strain energy to define the yield point [23]. By combining molecular dynamics with finite element method, and comparing three different potential energies: Lennard-Jones, modified Morse and reactive empirical bond-order, the mechanism of fracture expansion of carbon nanotubes was studied in [24]. Taking 'a bond's strain reaching 19% to be a broken bond' as a criterion for crack growing, an atomistic based finite element method for predicting the fracture behavior of graphene sheets was developed [25], and it was observed that graphene sheets are stiffer in the armchair direction than in the zigzag direction.

Even there are some successful experimental and numerical results, to save the simulation time and to get more trustable properties for nanomaterials are always the main targets in nanotechnology. With this in mind, recently we proposed a molecular-continuum model to predict the elastic properties of graphene sheets and carbon nanotubes [9]. By properly choosing the potential energy and applying a suitable deformation field, the stress-strain diagram of the estimated specimen can be plotted. If we

consider the turning point from increasing to decreasing of the stress-strain plot as the ultimate stress, it is possible to estimate the strength from the derivative of stress with respect to strain. Similar concept can be extended to the estimation of fracture toughness by introducing a counterpart – the strain intensity factor for the stress intensity factor. With this concept, in this paper the simulation was implemented by using the modified molecular-continuum model.

2. MOLECULAR-CONTINUUM MODEL FOR STRENGTH AND TOUGHNESS

In our previous study, a molecular-continuum model was proposed to estimate the mechanical properties of graphene sheets and carbon nanotubes [9]. The estimated properties are Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus which are defined based upon the initial linear region of stress-strain relation, and hence can be obtained by using small strains. To apply this model to predict the strength and fracture toughness, which occurs at the later period of the materials, a modification should be done on the last two stages of the model. The general procedure of the modified molecular-continuum model can be briefly stated as follows.

Estimation of strength

- (1) Select an appropriate representative volume element (RVE).
- (2) Determine the position of each atom of RVE in the undeformed state, which may be expressed as $\mathbf{r}_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i)$ for the i th atom of RVE.
- (3) Apply a suitable displacement field to RVE, and calculate the position of each atom in the deformed state, $\mathbf{r}'_i = (x'_i, y'_i, z'_i)$.
- (4) Calculate the distance change $\Delta\ell_{ij}$ between any two atoms and angle change $\Delta\alpha_{ijk}$ between any three atoms.
- (5) Calculate the potential energy U_e of RVE. In the present study, the modified Morse potential energy is used and

$$U_e = \sum_{i,j,k} D_e \{ [1 - e^{-\beta(\Delta\ell_{ij})}]^2 - 1 \} + \frac{1}{2} k_\theta (\Delta\alpha_{ijk})^2 [1 + k_s (\Delta\alpha_{ijk})^4], \quad (1)$$

where the parameters for graphene sheets are

$$\begin{aligned} D_e &= 0.6031 \text{ nN} \cdot \text{nm}, \beta = 26.25 \text{ nm}^{-1}, \\ k_\theta &= 0.9 \text{ nN} \cdot \text{nm/rad}^2, k_s = 0.754 \text{ rad}^{-4}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

- (6) Calculate the stresses σ_{ij} by differentiation of strain energy density, which is assumed to be equivalent to the mean value of potential energy, with respect to strains, i.e.,

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\partial U_e}{V_e \partial \varepsilon_{ij}}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \quad (3)$$

where V_e is the volume of RVE.

- (7) Plot the stress-strain diagram and use the diagram information to determine yield strength and ultimate strength.

Estimation of fracture toughness

- (1)-(5) Same as those stated for strength.
- (6) Calculate the stress intensity factor K_i by differentiation of energy release rate G with respect to strain intensity factor S_i , i.e.,

$$K_i = c_i \frac{\partial G}{\partial S_i}, \quad i = I, II, III, \quad (4)$$

where $G = dU_e / t da$, t is thickness of the specimen, and a is the length of crack. The coefficient c_i is a constant to adjust the equivalency of the relation (4), which can be found in [26]. The

equivalence of potential energy and elastic strain energy was assumed for the calculation of energy release rate. The strain intensity factors S_I and S_{II} are defined by

$$S_I = \lim_{\theta=0, r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi r} \varepsilon_y \quad \text{and} \quad S_{II} = \lim_{\theta=0, r \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi r} \gamma_{xy} \quad (5)$$

where ε_y and γ_{xy} are, respectively, normal strain and shear strain near the crack tip.

- (7) Plot the stress-strain intensity factor diagram and use the diagram information to determine fracture toughness.

The displacement field required in stage (3) is set to be the near tip solutions provided by linear elastic fracture mechanics, i.e., [27]

$$\begin{aligned} u_x &= \frac{K_I}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{r}{2\pi}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\kappa - 1 + 2\sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \right] + \frac{K_{II}}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{r}{2\pi}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\kappa + 1 + 2\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \right], \\ u_y &= \frac{K_I}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{r}{2\pi}} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\kappa + 1 - 2\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \right] - \frac{K_{II}}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{r}{2\pi}} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \left[\kappa - 1 - 2\sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where (r, θ) is the polar coordinate with the origin at the crack tip, K_I and K_{II} denote, respectively, the mode I (opening mode) and mode II (shearing mode) stress intensity factors, μ is shear modulus and $\kappa = (3 - \nu) / (1 + \nu)$ for plane stress condition where ν is Poisson's ratio.

3. GRAPHENE SHEET

Graphite has a layered structure and is stacked by graphene sheets with an interplanar spacing of 0.335 nm. In a graphene sheet, carbon atoms are arranged in a hexagonal pattern with bond length 0.142 nm and bond angle 120° (Figure 1). Adjacent graphene sheets are held together by weak van der Waals bonds, and hence, the in-plane elastic behavior of graphite can be represented by that of a graphene sheet due to the small influence from adjacent graphene sheets. From the atomic structure shown in Figure 2, the position of each atom of the graphene sheet in the undeformed state can be expressed in terms of a and α . For example, if the origin of the local coordinate locates on (x_0, y_0, z_0) , the position of atoms 1 and 2 of RVE of Figure 2 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_1 &= (x_1, y_1, z_1) = \left(\frac{a}{2} + x_0, y_0, z_0 \right), \quad \text{atom 1,} \\ \mathbf{r}_2 &= (x_2, y_2, z_2) = \left(\frac{a}{2} + a \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} + x_0, a \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} + y_0, z_0 \right), \quad \text{atom 2.} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The positions of all the other atoms can be obtained by using the condition of symmetry with respect to x - and y - axes.

Figure 1. Bond length, angle and thickness of graphene sheets [9]

Figure 2: RVE of graphene sheets for the estimation of strength

To estimate the strength an appropriate RVE consisting of six atoms (see Figure 2) is selected, whereas a circular RVE with the origin at the crack tip (see Figure 3) is selected for the estimation of fracture toughness. Table 1 shows the estimated results of yield strength and ultimate strength, in which the superscript (a) and (z) denote, respectively, the strength in the armchair and zigzag orientations. From this Table we see that the strength in armchair orientation is slightly higher than that in zigzag orientation, and our prediction is within the reasonable range provided by the authors using other methods. Figure 4(a) and Figure 4(b) are the predicted results of Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness versus crack length, which show that fracture toughness tends to a stable value when the crack length increases to a reasonable size.

Figure 3: RVE of graphene sheets for the estimation of fracture toughness (η is a constant related to Poisson's ration, which is generally near 0.5 [26].)

Yield strength	$\sigma_{ys}^{(a)}$ (GPa)	$\sigma_{ys}^{(z)}$ (GPa)
Present	25.98	23.21
Ultimate strength	$\sigma_{ult}^{(a)}$ (GPa)	$\sigma_{ult}^{(z)}$ (GPa)
Present	118.08	115.17
Baykasoglu and Mugaç [21]	105	90
Liu <i>et al.</i> [22]	118	115
Xu [28]	121	110
Zhao <i>et al.</i> [29]	98	83
Wang <i>et al.</i> [30]	107	90

Table 1: Yield strength and ultimate strength of graphene sheets.

Figure 4(a): Variation of mode I fracture toughness with respect to crack length.

Figure 4(b): Variation of mode II fracture toughness with respect to crack length.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The molecular-continuum model proposed previously for the estimation of elastic properties is modified in this paper to estimate the strength and fracture toughness of nanomaterials. The modified Morse potential energy is selected for the study of graphene sheets. The uniform strain field is applied for the estimation of yield strength and ultimate strength. The crack near tip displacement field provided by the linear elastic fracture mechanics is employed for the prediction of fracture toughness. With this selection for the modified molecular-continuum model, the numerical results presented in this study all fall in the reasonable range obtained by the other methods.

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